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**DOES THE INTERNET SHAPE OUR MIND? THE CASE OF VIRTUAL EMPATHY
IN FUTURE TEACHERS**

Loredana MANASIA, Teodora Daniela CHICIOREANU
University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest, Splaiul Independentei, Bucharest, Romania
loredana.manasia@upb.ro, teodora.chicioreanu@upb.ro

***Abstract:** There is no doubt that the use of technology and online activities shape our real-world interactions, thoughts, behaviours, attitudes, and affects. We take this as an opportunity to reconsider the digital competencies of future teachers. Therefore, the present paper argues the relevance of virtual empathy to fostering learning in virtual learning environments. To achieve this goal, a correlational study was conducted. A number of 569 undergraduate students, Z generation representatives, were purposefully sampled. All the participants were Internet users, enrolled in a teaching degree program in a Romanian regular university. The subjects completed an online survey measuring the level of virtual empathy, socio-demographics, and media usage behaviours. The self-report scale that we applied to measure participants' empathy levels has proved reliability. The article depicts the results of the study and discusses them. The results indicate a complex relation between going online and real-world empathy. Video gaming affects the level of virtual and real-world empathy. However, none of the participants reported optimal levels of virtual empathy. The scores of virtual empathy are significantly lower than those computed for real-world empathy (both for male and female subjects). Nevertheless, correlational analysis showed a positive and statistically significant correlation between the two types of empathy. In addition, gender differences regarding virtual empathy are analysed. In conclusion, the paper reflects on the need to reshape the view of digital literacy in future teachers.*

***Keywords:** virtual empathy; digital competence; teachers training; real-world empathy*

I. INTRODUCTION

Web 1.0 changed the world but Web 2.0 changed the people. Our social worlds are going digital [9] and the impact of the transformation is still difficult to assess and comprehend [17]. Moreover, the Internet is not “a monolithic or placeless cyberspace; rather it is numerous new technologies used by diverse people in diverse real world locations, as Miller and Slater [12] argue.

The momentous inception of the web 1.0 highly affected the way people generate and use information. The process of digitalization started and provoked tremendous reactions conducting to the revolution of information and people’s power instauration. With the web 2.0, social activities became digital and the technologically- mediated communication resulted extremely powerful. Pangrazio [14] states that the success of young persons is strongly related to the digital literacy (p. 163). As Chase and Laufenberg [1] warn that without this ability, the students ‘will be left behind’.

The article considers the relevance of real life empathy (RLE) and virtual empathy (VE) in the context of initial training of future teachers. A general model of empathy is identified and discussed in relation to two key components such as cognitive empathy and affective empathy. In the present study, we aimed at assessing the level of real life and virtual empathy in future teachers and the association of these variables with the subjects’ digital personality and presence in online environments. Several research questions guided the research design and data collection process:

Q1. Does the online activity affect real life empathy?

Q2. Which is the relation between real life empathy and virtual empathy?

1.1 Teachers and digital intelligence

The social and economic impact of technology is still difficult to comprehend. If our world is going digital, the teachers – as actors of the knowledge sharing process – need to be savvy with technology. One of the biggest challenges is to foster digital intelligence through academic curriculum for teachers training. In this paper, we emphasize the pivotal role of digital intelligence and literacy in higher education in general and especially in future teachers training.

The current article differentiates between digital intelligence (DQ) and digital literacy. Following the CHC theory on the structure of the human cognitive abilities [11], the authors propose to see DQ as a single general ability meanwhile digital literacy is a broad ability. DQ refers to a set of social, emotional, cognitive, and technical abilities that enable individuals to face the challenges and adapt to the demand of digital life [5]. DQ is considered a different intelligence emerging from human – computer interaction. Instead, digital literacy refers to the multiplicity of literacies associated with the use of digital technologies [13]. Digital intelligence is a growing area of research and practice, yet the question of how to define it remains largely unresolved. The consequences resulted in overly broad definitions of the concept [14]. As other scholars comment, the broad definitions of DQ fail to focus on defining the essential features of the concept. In our understanding, a general model of digital intelligence comprises several key components such as digital identity, digital use, safety, security, and digital emotional intelligence, communication in digital environments, rights, and literacy. In this structure, the virtual empathy is a component of digital emotional intelligence.

1.2 Virtual empathy

The study of empathy in educational contexts is not cutting edge. Much research has been done in this field since its inception in 1906. Theodor Lipps is considered a pioneer in the conceptualization of empathy. What is new is the study of virtual empathy. As Cohen and Strayer [2] state, empathy refers to the understanding of and sharing in another's emotional state or context. In Romanian empathy scientific literature, the concept is referred usually as *psychological transposition*. Fernández-Pinto, López-Pérez, and Márquez [4] argue that empathy needs to be approached from a triple perspective involving cognitive, emotional and situational aspects. In the conceptualization of empathy, the scholars usually distinguish between the *affective* (the capacity to experience the emotions of another) and the *cognitive* (the ability to comprehend other's emotions) dimensions of empathy. Drawing from this bidimensional approach of empathy, we have designed the present study.

The use of digital communication means tend to reduce face-to-face communication and thus the empathic skill, state Carrier et al [3]. In addition, Konrath [8] suggest a potential decline in various personality variables of the net generation. Consequently, the hypothesis of superficial digital interactions leading to lower levels of empathy was launched. Building on the fact that not so much research has been conducted on virtual empathy, Carrier et al. [3] argue that one can be empathic in computer-mediated communication. The cited authors [3] enlist a corpus of studies that have identified empathic behaviour in online environments such as social networks, bulletin boards, and communities of practice or of interest.

II. METHOD

2.1 Participants

A number of 569 students participated in this descriptive research study. To select them, the authors applied a purposive sampling procedure. All the subjects in the sample were students of a technical university and were enrolled in a teacher initial training programme. They were being trained to be teachers in the lower secondary education cycle. Table 1 synthetizes the socio-demographical characteristics of the subjects in the investigated sample. All the participants were internet users. Almost 38% of them are heavy users, spending a large amount of time on the internet and engaging in gaming, file sharing, or video sharing activities. Medium users are less well represented in the sample (29%). Light users cover 33% of the sample.

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Female	322	56,6
	Male	247	43,4
Age	< 21	372	65,4
	21-23	162	28,5
	>23	35	6,2
Year	First	168	29,5
	Second	289	50,8
	Third	112	19,7

Table 1. Socio-demographic profile of the subjects in the sample (N = 569)

All the subjects participated voluntarily in the project and did not receive any incentive.

2.2 Instruments

Basic Empathy Scale. To measure the levels of empathy we adapted and applied the Basic Empathy Scale – BES [7]. This self-report scale comprises 20 items generated based on the conceptualization of cognitive and affective empathy [7]. Nine of the items assess cognitive empathy; meanwhile affective empathy is investigated through eleven items. As Jolliffe and Farrington [7] state, in the case of effective empathy the subject experiences congruent emotions with the target-person. Cognitive empathy refers to a person's ability to recognize and comprehend the emotions of another person [3]. Items on the scale were rated on a five-point Likert scale starting from 1 (strongly disagree) and ending with 5 (strongly agree). The three point was associated with a neutral response. The initial version of the BES has proven good to excellent reliabilities for the two subscales as follows: $\alpha_{cognitive} = .79$ and $\alpha_{affective} = .85$. Similar coefficients were computed for the version we have applied in the present study $\alpha = .82$ for the entire scale, with positive interitem correlations above the .42 threshold. The confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) validated the two factors solution. The two factors were allowed to correlate. The loadings of the items in the cognitive empathy scale varied between 0.47 and 0.73. The affective empathy items' loadings ranged from 0.53 to 0.89.

Virtual empathy scale. To measure the levels of virtual empathy in the selected sample an adapted version of BES was designed by the authors. Each item in the aforementioned scale was adapted to express clearly an interaction or a situation in a digital environment. Carrier and his collaborators [3] applied a similar procedure. Thus, the initial Basic Empathy Scale resulted in Virtual Basic Empathy Scale (VBES). The reliabilities of all the scale are good $\alpha > .76$.

Digital Personality Questionnaire. To assess activities and behaviours in digital environments the Digital Personality Questionnaire was designed. The instrument comprises seven dimensions: (1) *personalization* of the digital activity; (2) *social media* usage and entertainment; (3) *eCommerce*; (4) *mobile usage*; (5) *leisure time* activities; (6) *gaming*; (7) *life perception* and *social values*. The last part was dedicated to socio-demographical characteristics of the subjects (gender, age, year of study). All these dimensions resulted in 62 items. In the first section of the questionnaire, we were interested to investigate if the subjects invest time and effort to sample digital niche content (e.g. customized start pages, browser recommendations, news feeds, scheduled updates, and widgets). In addition to the items in the first section, the respondents answered questions related to the social media usage and entertainment. The items were related to blogging (reading, commenting, and writing), social networks activities, social bookmarking websites, photosharing websites, music and videostreaming sites, and news consumption. The authors focused on assessing whether the subjects' behaviors range from a passive usage to content creation.

Further, each section of the questionnaire included items related to the daily media usage hours.

2.3 Procedure

To support the research framework, the authors preferred a descriptive and transversal research design. Web Assisted Personal Interviewing (WAPI) is the technique we applied to collect data. Thus, the questionnaires have been self-administrated through the Survey Gizmo online data

collection platform. The completion rate was about 65% (as computed by the data collection platform) resulting in 569 complete responses. The average completion time was 27 minutes.

2.4 Data analysis

The quantitative data collected through the BES, VBES, and Digital Personality Questionnaire were analysed by applying statistical techniques. In addition to descriptive statistics, confirmatory and exploratory factor analyses have been performed. CFA has been applied to test the two-factor solution in BES and VBES scales. Principal components analysis (PCA) with Varimax rotation and Kaiser Normalization has been conducted to segment the subjects according to their digital behaviours and attitudes. The four segments will be described in subsequent sections of the paper. Pearson bi-variate correlations (two-tailed) were carried out, as well as variance analyses (ANOVA).

III. RESULTS

Digital Personality Types. The PCA analysis revealed *four types of digital personalities* among future teachers: (1) *the silent user*; (2) *the novel consumer*; (3) *the versatile user*; (4) *the digital expert*. The segmentation in the Table 2 explains almost 60% of the variation.

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4,81	27,599	27,599	4,816	27,599	27,599	4,164	23,865	23,865
2	2,36	13,548	41,147	2,364	13,548	41,147	1,848	10,591	34,457
3	1,46	8,404	49,551	1,466	8,404	49,551	2,062	11,815	46,271
4	1,36	7,819	57,370	1,364	7,819	57,370	1,937	11,098	57,370

Table 2. Total variance explained

The Silent Users (SU) represent 22 percent of the investigated sample (see Table 3). This is the less active segment in digital environments. They are acting like gatekeepers seeing and reading articles, news, posts, and sometimes sharing the information. Usually, the SUs do not play videogames. Instead, they use social networks as a replacement of chat or email. The virtual social field of these users is fairly small and thoroughly checked. The SUs' circle of friends replicates real life relations (including family members). It is possible to use a nickname instead of the real one.

The Novel Consumer (NOC) is slightly more active and engaged to digital activities than the Silent User. These users carefully select their friends. They prefer to consume information rather than to produce it. The NOCs read news, blogs, listen to the music, share pictures r videos and play simple games. The actively seek for information in digital environments. Most of the NOCs do not neglect their digital image. They update constantly their profiles.

The Versatile Users (VU) are one of the most active segments in digital life. VUs use several social networks (including the professional ones), read news websites, play games, upload and create information, use online apps to manage time or personal projects, and comment to various topics. For VUs, the social networks are a mean of self-promotion.

The Digital Experts (EXP) are the most active type of digital personality. They are eager to have a large number of online friends and followers. In the same line of thoughts, they seek for digital social recognition. The EXPs are interested in exploring and testing various apps. They create digital content (including videos and tutorials), share opinions on blogs or social networks. They have the potential to become digital trendsetters.

All the clusters in the sample added to their digital friends lists close friends (94.9%). The versatile users and the experts also follow online influencers like bloggers, vloggers or else. The silent users are those who added their family and relatives to the online friend list (88.2%, n = 125).

Segment	Frequency	Percent
Novel consumers	147.2	26
Digital protagonists	131.4	23
Versatile users	165.6	29
Silent users	125.2	22

Table 3. The distribution of the four segments in the sample (N=569)

When they go online, the VUs and the EXPs prefer long sessions although they are not constantly active. Meanwhile, the SUs and the NOCs tend to limit their online sessions. When visiting Facebook and YouTube, all the segments spend more than 30 minutes. Slightly over 10 percent spend more than 120 minutes on Facebook and YouTube in a sole session.

All the four segments prefer to spend their free time with their friends and life partners. In addition, the SUs and NOCs tend to appreciate the time spent with their families; meanwhile the VUs and the EXPs are interested to share time and experiences with their fellows.

As the research revealed, friendship and the freedom to schedule the leisure time represent fundamental values for all the clusters in the sample. Only six percent of the sample prefer to stay alone during leisure times.

Digital activities cover a significant period of an ordinary day (see Table 4). Surfing websites, visiting the online pages of the social networks or chatting are dominant activities in the subjects' digital life. The bellow table suggests the presence of 'in risk' activities such as reading for pleasure, using learning management systems or emailing.

Activities	Mean hours	Standard deviation (SD)
Attending courses	4.23	3.21
Meeting people	3.73	2.97
Surfing websites	3.72	2.65
Texting	3.27	2.34
Visiting the social networks websites	3.13	2.93
Listening to music (online)	2.71	2.67
Listening to music (offline)	0.9	1.02
Chatting	2.63	1.23
Studying	2.43	0.9
Resting	2.20	2.23
Talking on the phone	1.62	1.47
Plying video or console games (alone or in group)	1.32	1.54
Watching TV	1.20	0.9
Taking long walks	1.20	1.2
Shopping in stationary stores	0.92	
Emailing	0.91	
Reading for pleasure	0.73	
Virtual worlds	0.71	
Online shopping	0.61	
Video calls	0.34	1.27
Using learning management systems	0.23	0.9

Table 4. Activities performed on a typical day by the subjects in the sample (N = 569)

Most of the subjects in the sample prefer the mobile phone and instant messaging to communicate with their families and relatives (see Figure 1).

Real life and virtual empathy levels. To analyse real life empathy in future teachers, the authors created a new variable representing the real life empathy score (RLE) – as a mean of the scores of the twenty items in the scale. The values of the RLE variable ranged from 2.00 to 4.86, $Mean_{RLE} = 3.64, SD = 0.59$. As García-Pérez et al. [6] proposed, the RLE variable was recoded into a different variable (RLE-rec) to compute the levels of empathy. Four levels were identified: Deficient (ranging from 1 – 2), Basic (2.1 – 3), Median (3.1 – 4), Optimal (4.1 – 5). This score of RLE

corresponds to a medium level of empathy. The frequency analysis revealed that almost half of the subjects have a medium level of RLE (50.4%). Lower levels of RLE (deficient and basic) are characteristics of 17.2% of the sample. The difference of 32.3 percent corresponds to undergraduates with optimal level of RLE.

As for the virtual empathy, the authors applied the same procedure. A new variable was created (VE) as a mean score of the all items in the virtual empathy scale. VE ranged from 1 through 3.63 ($Mean_{VE} = 2.29, SD = 0.91$). By applying the same recoding labels, the authors computed the levels of VE. The majority of the subjects (73.3%) proved low levels of VE (see Table 5). None of the subjects has an optimal level of the virtual empathy.

On the subject of cognitive and emotional virtual empathy, the undergraduates develop more favourably the cognitive dimension: $Mean_{cognitive} = 3.62, SD = 0.9$; $Mean_{emotional} = 2.57, SD = 0.78$. Analysing the items in the scale of virtual empathy, interesting findings could be revealed. For example, the subjects registered low scores for the following items: I feel glad if someone in my list has achieved something; when I see that a person in my list has a new job or a new house I usually feel joy. My online friends' unhappiness does not affect me too much (reverse coding).

Level	Frequency	Percent
Deficient	197	34.6
Basic	220	38.7
Median	152	26.7
Optimal	0	0

Table 5. The levels of virtual empathy of the trainee teachers (N = 569)

Figure 1. Means to communicate with friends and relatives (N = 569)

The relation between online activities and levels of real life empathy. From the items in the Table 4, there have been selected those referring to online activities (even they involve using a mobile phone, a tablet, a laptop or a desktop): surfing websites, visiting the social networks' websites, chatting, playing videogames, emailing, listening to music online, using learning management systems, online shopping, virtual worlds, and video calls. A new variable (digital activities time – DAT). Pearson's r coefficient was computed for all the aforementioned items: $0.33 \leq r \leq .69$. The mean time spent for online activities is 16.31 hours per day ($SD = 6.72$). First, the authors were

interested in calculating the correlations between the DAT and RLE variables. All the correlations are negative and indicate a weak association between the RLE and DAT variables (see Table 6). The same observation is valid for the two dimensions of the RLE: cognitive and emotional real life empathy. Thus, we can observe that going online has a very small impact on real life empathy and both on cognitive and emotional empathy.

Variable	Digital activities time
Real life empathy	-0.23
Cognitive RLE	-0.20
Emotional RLE	-0.27

Table 6. Pearson's r correlation between DAT and RLE

To investigate if the strength of the association between RLE and DAT varies with the number of hours spent with meeting people a linear regression model was designed. The gender of subjects was added to the model. The regression analysis conducted us to conclude that the gender variable has a β coefficient significantly higher than 0 ($\beta = 0.19, p = 0.00$). As for the meeting people variable, $\beta = 0.031, p = .671$. Thus, there are differences between male and female subjects regarding RLE. Meeting people and spending time with them is not a powerful mediator of the association between RLE and DAT.

Concerning the gender differences, the Wilcoxon test for paired samples is statistically significant ($p = .00, Mean_{RLEfemale} = 3.37, SD = .67; Mean_{RLEmale} = 2.85, SD = .60$).

The relation between real life empathy and virtual empathy. First, the authors investigated the associations between the RLE and VE variables. Table 7 presents the results of the analysis.

The results show there is a statistically significant moderate association between RLE and VE ($r = .597, p = .00$). The observation is valid for the correlations between the two dimensions of the RLE and those of VE. The mean scores for the cognitive and affective dimensions of RLE and VE have been compared. Repeated Measures ANOVA was applied (real life versus virtual empathy and cognitive versus affective empathy). The F test is statistically significant: $F(1,567) = 1838.003, p = .00$. Thus, the scores of RLE are significantly higher than those computed for VE. In the case of cognitive and affective empathy, the scores for cognitive empathy are significantly higher: $F(1,567) = 2042.859, = .00$.

Variable	1	3	4	5
1. RLE	-			
2. VE	.597**			
3. Real life cognitive	.-			
4. Real life affective	-	.422*	-	
5. Virtual cognitive	-	.523**	.354**	-
6. Virtual affective	-	.427*	.541**	.423**
Note. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$				

Table 7. Pearson's r correlations between RLE and VE

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, we aimed at assessing the levels of real life and virtual empathy in trainee teachers. In addition, the digital personality of the subjects in the sample has been investigated. The results of the study revealed the presence of four clusters in the sample, according to their digital behaviours and attitudes, namely the Silent Users, the Novel Consumers, the Versatile Users, and the Experts. The majority of the subjects in the sample portrayed a traditional values system in the centre of which are their families, friends, and the future career. Concerning the attitudes reported by the undergraduates, the study revealed the presence of the social pessimism [16]. Following this line of thoughts, their potential failures are consequences of a malfunctioning society. The subjects' expectations from life are built around two cores: personal and professional success. The

representatives of the Z generation value the leisure time activities. Even if they do not plan their leisure time, young people are satisfied with the way they spend it.

The virtual empathy is a component of digital intelligence, considered a core ability in the context of the emerging information societies and economies [15]. In the context of the present study, we measured both the real life and virtual empathy. The subjects reported a medium level of real life empathy ($Mean_{RLE} = 3.64, SD = 0.59$) and a basic level of virtual empathy ($Mean_{VE} = 2.29, SD = 0.91$). From all the subjects, 32.3 percent showed an optimal level of RLE, while none of them reported an optimal level of VE. As García-Peñalvo et al. [5] argue the nature of digital interactions and the reasons for website browsing or social networks usage could be the factors explaining the variance of these low scores of virtual empathy. Most of the users stated they surf the Internet to entertain themselves, to search for information, and to shop. When visiting the websites of the social networks, 34 percent of future teachers read on a daily basis what other persons write, 30 percent share and tag pictures, 21 percent play games. Only 10% (mostly the VUs and the EXPs) comment to friends' posts on a daily basis. A slightly higher number (11%) share information on their profile and only 5 percent promote a social cause. However, we can conclude that most of the digital activities does not involve a real human interaction. The subjects tend to communicate with those persons they frequently interact with in real life activities.

The research also found differences between male and female subjects (the score are higher for females). The results are consistent with those discussed in previous studies [6], [3], [10]. In parallel, the study presents reliable instruments to research the virtual empathy levels and the digital personality of the Z generation.

Further studies could focus on comparative approaches of students being trained exclusively to become teachers and students with a double certification (as the case of this study). Moreover, the analysis of the curriculum of the teachers' training academic programs could lead to interesting findings on the contribution of school of the development of digital intelligence and virtual empathy.

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